

LET'S ABOLISH THE EDUCATION REQUIREMENT FOR PROFESSIONAL CERTIFICATION: AN ANALYSIS FROM THE PERSPECTIVES OF LAW, ECONOMICS & ETHICS

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Abstract

A number of accounting and auditing certifications require some amount of university education. The AICPA requires its new members to have 150 semester hours of coursework and is pushing the states to adopt the 150 semester hour requirement as a condition of qualifying to take the CPA exam.

This paper takes the opposite approach. Rather than increasing the amount of education needed to take the CPA exam, this author advocates abolishing the education requirement altogether.

Introduction

Most professional accounting certifications require some university education as a condition of taking their certification exams.² The American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

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² Another, more basic question is whether there should even be a licensing requirement for accountants. However, we will not get into a discussion of that issue here. This question has been addressed in Robert W. McGee, *Let's Abolish Licensure Laws for Accountants: An Analysis from the Perspectives of Law, Economics & Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998). For a general discussion of licensure laws, see Robert W. McGee, *Occupational Licensure Laws: An Economic and Ethical Analysis*, 2 COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS (1998).

(AICPA) requires new members to have completed 150 semester hours (about 5 years) of coursework. A number of state CPA societies have convinced their legislatures to require 150 semester hours of credit in order to take the CPA exam in their state.³ This education requirement is going in exactly the wrong direction.

Perhaps 75% to 80% of the present education requirement consists of nonaccounting courses. Regional and national accrediting rules⁴ require accounting students to take about 50% of their coursework in liberal arts and another 25% or so in business courses other than accounting. Accounting students are not able to take more than about 25% of their coursework in accounting even if they want to. In the fifth year, some schools do not have any accounting requirement whatsoever. Students are encouraged to take nonaccounting courses in order to broaden their perspective.

³ For some discussions of the 150 semester hour requirement, see Robert W. McGee, *The Economics and Ethics of Requiring 150 Semester Hours of Coursework to Sit for the CPA Exam*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Spring 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Some Ethical Problems with the 150 Semester Hour Accounting Education Requirement*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Fall 1998); Priscilla M. Austin and Daniel J. O'Mara, *An Evaluation of the 150-Semester Hour Educational Requirement*, PENNSYLVANIA CPA JOURNAL 18-21 (Fall 1989); Larry Deppe, Don R. Hansen and Stan Jenne, *The 150-Hour Educational Requirement: The History and Message of the Utah Experience*, 2 ACCOUNTING HORIZONS 53-57 (June 1988); Paul Clolery, *The Debate Intensifies over the 150-Hour Rule*, 25 THE PRACTICAL ACCOUNTANT 74-80 (December 1992); Committee on Education and Experience Requirements for CPAs, *Report of the Committee on Education and Experience Requirements for CPAs* (Beamer Report), (New York: AICPA, 1969); David J. Ortinau, Terry J. Engle and Jerry D. Siebel, *Attitudinal Insights into the Costs and Benefits of a Mandated Postbaccalaureate Education Requirement*, 3 ACCOUNTING HORIZONS 86-94 (March 1989); AICPA, *Education Requirements for Entry into the Accounting Profession, a statement of AICPA policies* (New York: AICPA, 1988).

⁴ There are six regional accrediting agencies in the United States. There is one national accreditation agency that accredits business schools, the American Assembly of Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB). Although nominally in the private sector, these agencies all receive their authority and recognition from the U.S. Department of Education, which has granted them a monopoly. Federal student loans can be made only to students who attend accredited institutions.

Part of this liberal arts "mentality" is the result of the misguided belief that certified public accountants need to be more than accountants. The International Federation of Accountants is pushing this belief on a worldwide basis. In its Handbook, it states:

The goal of accounting education and experience must be to produce competent professional accountants capable of making a positive contribution over their lifetimes to the profession and society in which they work.⁵

Why should an accountant have to make a contribution to "society" in order to be certified? It might reasonably be argued that an accountant who seeks to cut cost or reduce taxes for his employer might be making a larger contribution to "society" than does an accountant who runs around trying to be a do-gooder. It is just Adam Smith's Invisible Hand at work in the field of accounting.⁶

The IFAC Handbook goes on to say:

All cultures exist in an environment of significant change. Increasingly, today's professional accountants, in addition to acquiring accounting skills and knowledge, must have skills that enable them to be entrepreneurs, financial analysts, excellent sales persons, good communicators, capable negotiators and public relations specialists, as well as good managers. A program of accounting education and experience must go beyond the

⁵ International Federation of Accountants, IFAC HANDBOOK 1998: TECHNICAL PRONOUNCEMENTS 597 ¶7 (New York, International Federation of Accountants, 1998).

⁶ ADAM SMITH, THE WEALTH OF NATIONS (1776).

traditional approach to accounting education, which has emphasized "transfer of knowledge," with learning defined and measured strictly in terms of knowledge of principles, standards, concepts, facts, and procedures at a point in time. Emphasis must be placed on a set of knowledge, skills, and professional values broad enough to enable adaption to change. Individuals who become professional accountants should be characterized by a constant striving to learn and apply what is new.⁷

There are several problems with this philosophical approach. For one thing, not all accountants need to be entrepreneurs. In fact, most of them cannot be entrepreneurs due to the nature of their job. The vast majority of accountants report to someone else. Entrepreneurs must be able to "call the shots." Most accountants are not in a position to do so. Furthermore, it is doubtful that university programs have the capability of training entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs are born, not made.

Not all accountants need to be financial analysts. Accountants who work in the areas of cost accounting, taxation, data processing, nonprofit accounting and auditing have little or no use for financial analyst skills. Furthermore, what knowledge they need in this area can be had by taking a few accounting courses. Taking liberal arts courses will not help them to achieve this goal.

Very few accountants need to be excellent salespersons or any kind of salespersons. Most accountants do not deal with the public in a sales capacity. The only accountants who need to be excellent salespersons are the partners in public accounting firms, who need to generate business. Even these people can get by quite nicely without being excellent salespersons.

Individuals in any field could benefit by being good communicators. Accountants are not the only ones who need good communication skills. But it does not follow that the accounting

⁷ *Id.*, at ¶8.

curriculum needs to restrict the number of accounting courses students can take so that they can take more communications courses. Communications departments,⁸ along with education departments,⁹ are the laughing stock of American universities. Everyone knows that their programs are far from rigorous. Requiring accounting students to take more courses in nonrigorous disciplines at the expense of not being able to take more rigorous courses in the accounting department is exactly the wrong way to go. Not only is the public interest not being protected by such a requirement, it is actually being harmed.

Negotiation skills come in handy for some accountants, especially those who have to deal with the Internal Revenue Service. But for most other accountants negotiation skills are not needed any more than they are needed by other business people. Even if negotiation skills are needed, the universities do not do a very good job of developing such skills. Very few university curricula include a course on negotiation skills. Perhaps negotiation skills can best be learned in the real world.

Some people need to be public relations specialists but many do not. Many accountants, especially in industry, never see the general public. The need to be a good manager is also a skill that only a few accountants need to possess. Most accountants have no one to manage but themselves. No one should be denied the right to take a professional certification exam just because they have not had a management course at the college level.

⁸ The communications majors who take my financial accounting class do significantly worse on exams than do the rest of the class. Interestingly enough, they do not even do well at writing term papers. So what are they learning in the communications department anyway?

⁹ The author was once enrolled in the PhD program of one of the more prestigious university education departments in the New York City area. The course on tests and measurements consisted of spending one week each talking about multiple choice questions, essay questions, matching and fill in the blank questions, and eleven weeks reviewing what we had learned in the previous three weeks. The teacher for that class should be commended for being able to stretch so little material so far.

Finally, even if it is conceded that accountants need to be all of these things, entrepreneurs, salespersons, managers and all the rest, it does not follow that they should be precluded from taking a certification exam until they have taken all these courses. Ideally, education is a lifelong process. Most education takes place outside the classroom. If these skills can be acquired, they can be acquired outside as well as inside the classroom. Requiring people to take classes in these subjects before they can sit for a certification exam makes no sense. All it does is artificially restrict entry into the accounting profession, which increases costs without necessarily increasing the quality of the product that is offered. In fact, some studies have found that restricting entry into professions actually decreases the quality of the services provided.¹⁰

It is worrisome that the various governments around the world, influenced by accounting associations that are pushing for lengthening the amount of education that is needed in order to acquire these tangential skills, are passing laws that force accountants to prolong their education and greatly increase its cost so that they can acquire skills that are, at best, of marginal benefit to the average accountant. Many of these tangential skills can either be learned on the job or cannot be learned at all. Yet the people who make the laws would force accountants to spend time and money trying to learn such things as part of a university education.

Legal Reasons for Abolishing the Education Requirement

The only legitimate reason for government to exist is to protect life, liberty and property. Government should protect people from fraud, internal and external aggression and otherwise leave people alone to live their own lives. The public interest is

¹⁰ Some of these studies are cited in Robert W. McGee, *Let's Abolish Licensure Laws for Accountants: An Analysis from the Perspectives of Law, Economics & Ethics*, 1 JOURNAL OF ACCOUNTING, ETHICS & PUBLIC POLICY (Summer 1998); Robert W. McGee, *Occupational Licensure Laws: An Economic and Ethical Analysis*, 2 COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS (1998).

not served by requiring a university education as a condition of sitting for a certification exam. If the exam tests the knowledge it is supposed to test, the public will be as well served as would be the case in the absence of a university education requirement. If the test does not measure what it is supposed to measure, having an education requirement will not help protect the public interest. From a legal standpoint, there is no reason to have an education requirement as a condition for taking a certification exam.

Economic Reasons for Abolition

The main economic reason for abolishing the education requirement is that major cost savings can result if students are no longer required to have 4 or 5 years of university education as a requirement for taking a certification exam. They will be able to accumulate enough technical knowledge by taking just one year of coursework (30 semester hours). The public interest would not be any better protected if they were forced to take an additional three or four years of coursework that has nothing to do with accounting. How is the public interest served by forcing students to take English literature, history, etc. when these subjects have nothing to do with accounting?

Ethical Reasons for Abolition

The primary ethical reason for abolishing the education requirement is that the education requirement is a barrier to entry into the accounting profession. It is unethical to prevent someone from earning a livelihood by raising barriers to entry that do nothing to protect the public from fraud or incompetence. The market has traditionally done a better job of protecting the public than has government.¹¹ No one becomes more competent to

¹¹ For discussions on this point, see MILTON FRIEDMAN, *CAPITALISM & FREEDOM* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1962); MILTON AND ROSE FRIEDMAN, *FREE TO CHOOSE*; Robert W. McGee, *Occupational Licensure Laws: An Economic and Ethical Analysis*, 2 COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS (1998); S. DAVID YOUNG, *THE RULE OF EXPERTS: OCCUPATIONAL LICENSING IN AMERICA* (Washington, DC: The Cato Institute, 1987); SIMON ROTTENBERG

perform accounting tasks by taking 50% of an undergraduate curriculum in liberal arts. Having an education requirement is at best misguided and at worst a self-serving example of rent-seeking. There is no ethical reason to require anyone to pay for and sit through five years of university education when all they need is about 30 semester hours of coursework (one year) to become competent entry-level accountants.

Concluding Comments

What would happen if the education requirement were abolished and people were able to take the CPA or other certification exams without first having four or five years of university training?¹² Perhaps the pass rate would decline, since some people who have less than a full university level education would be taking the exam. But the pass rate could also increase, because some people, rather than spending four or five years taking coursework that is 75% to 80% irrelevant might decide to take just 60 hours of coursework that is just in accounting, which is twice as much as they can now take under present accreditation rules. So they would be better prepared as accountants. Also, since

(ED.), OCCUPATIONAL LICENSURE AND REGULATION (Washington, DC: American Enterprise Institute, 1980).

¹² It should be pointed out that this question is utilitarian based, and thus is not legitimate from an ethical standpoint. If rights are being violated, it is not legitimate to ask what would happen if rights stopped being violated. The same question was asked in the decades before the War for Southern Independence [history books refer to it as the Civil War], when some abolitionists feared that freeing the slaves immediately would cause hardship on the slave owners and would throw the slaves into unemployment. They advocated gradualism as a means of overcoming the hardships that would otherwise result. Where rights are concerned, it is never legitimate to ask what would happen if rights were no longer violated. The rights violations must simply be stopped and let the chips fall where they may. For discussions on the structural flaws of all utilitarian arguments, see Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in the Methodology of Law & Economics*, 1 COMMENTARIES ON LAW & ECONOMICS 209-223 (1997); Robert W. McGee, *The Fatal Flaw in NAFTA, GATT and All Other Trade Agreements*, 14 NORTHWESTERN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW & BUSINESS 549-565 (1994).

the barrier to entry has been reduced,¹³ more people would be likely to enter the accounting profession and take the certification exam.

There is no valid reason for having an education requirement to sit for a certification exam. The exam itself should serve as a measure of educational qualification. Preventing individuals from earning a livelihood is not a legitimate function of government. The requirement is costly, both to the students who would like to sit for the CPA exam and for that segment of the public that hires accounting services, since the reduced supply of accountants is bound to raise fees in the accounting profession. The requirement is also unethical. It should be abolished.

¹³ The barrier to entry would be reduced by abolishing all education requirements. However, it would not be eliminated because people would still have to take and pass the certification exam.